

Social Support and Academic Procrastination Tendency for Students Working on Thesis in the Covid-19 Pandemic

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Abstract:- The Covid-19 pandemic had several negative impacts, including delaying the thesis completion, which has increased compared to before the pandemic. This study aims to determine the relationship between social support and academic procrastination in students working on their thesis during the pandemic. There were 161 participants and the purposive sampling technique was used. Furthermore, this study used a quantitative design with a correlational method. The hypothesis proposed a significant negative relationship between social support and academic procrastination in these students. Furthermore, the Tuckman Procrastination Scale and the Interpersonal Support Evaluation List were employed. Also, the data analysis was conducted using *Statistical Product and Service Solutions (SPSS) version 24 for Windows*. Before testing the hypothesis, several statistical tests were carried out, such as the assumption test, which included the normality and linearity test. The results showed that there was a significant negative relationship between social support and academic procrastination in the students, and the correlation coefficient value obtained was $r = -0.380$ and $p = 0.000$ ($p < 0.05$). This indicates that the higher the level of social support obtained by students, the lower the academic procrastination behavior carried out, and vice versa. Therefore, the hypothesis in this study is accepted. Several additional analyzes were conducted in this study, including the correlation of social support variables, academic procrastination and its various tests based on predetermined demographics.

Keywords:- Social Support, Academic Procrastination, Final Year Students working on Thesis.

I. INTRODUCTION

Academic procrastination is a tendency to delay and avoid an activity conducted under individual control (Tuckman, 1991). Academic procrastination is a pattern of behavior with serious consequences for the perpetrator, marked by deadlines that are encountered in individual academic lives (Tuckman, 2005). Academic procrastination has 3 aspects namely a general self-description of the tendency to deal with things, a tendency to avoid the unpleasantness and to have difficulty, and a tendency to blame others for one's plight, respectively (Tuckman, 1991).

Currently, the existence of the Covid-19 virus has a global impact. Consequently, the government imposed a physical distancing policy, resulting in the implementation of distance learning in universities to reduce the risk of transmission. This policy created various problems, such as the lack of a conducive learning environment that requires intensive guidance from lecturers and positive interactions with fellow students, especially for final year students working on their thesis (Khoirunnisa et al., 2021). Also, there is the issue of academic procrastination (Fadila & Khoirunnisa, 2021).

During the pandemic, the academic procrastination level of these students increased and was classified in the medium category. The survey was conducted on 36 students working on a thesis during the X majoring pandemic at a state university class in 2017 in a study by Fadila & Khoirunnisa (2021). About 83% of 36 students agreed that the pandemic caused an increase in academic procrastination. According to a study by Khoirunnisa et al (2021), the academic procrastination of final year students during the pandemic is moderate, with about 140 students or 72% of the total participants. A total of 27 students, making up 14%, were in the high category, while 27 students were in the low category.

Increased procrastination occurs because of the challenges in thesis writing during the pandemic due to the implementation which differs prior to the outbreak. Previously, thesis guidance was completed in person, now it is conducted online. This online tutoring cannot fulfill students' curiosity about their thesis, hence it has not been implemented properly (Lestari & Wulandari, 2021). Due to the closure of the study location, students who conducted a direct study in the field and looked for reference sources in the library, experienced limited movement in data collection and searching for reference sources (Khoirunnisa et al., 2021).

High and low academic procrastination have an impact on students. Students with low academic procrastination have a flow experience, such as positive feelings, pleasure, and satisfaction (Pradana & Putri, 2019). Meanwhile, high academic procrastination leads to maladaptive behaviors, such as low academic performance and achievement (Kim & Seo, 2015). Previous studies demonstrated that this procrastination is associated with poor academic performance (Wesley, 1994), hence a source of personal stress (Tice & Baumeister, 1997). There are also physical, affective, and psychological impacts. The effect in terms of

physical, which involves fatigue and difficulty sleeping, and affective, such as anxiety, fear, regret, stress, uncontrollable emotions, and panic (Suhadianto & Pratitis., 2020).

The factors affecting academic procrastination include internal and external factors. These internal factors include fear of failure (Solomon & Rothblum, 1984), task aversion (Solomon & Rothblum, 1984), negative perception of the task (Solomon & Rothblum, 1984), physical condition (Fauziah, 2015), time management (Fauziah, 2015), and sense of laziness (Fauziah, 2015). However, the external factors include parenting (Vahedi et al., 2009) environmental conditions (Wangid, 2014), social support (Harmalis et al., 2021), and academic environment (Suhadianto & Pratitis., 2020)

This study used social support as a factor that affects academic procrastination. Social support refers to various resources provided by one's interpersonal relationships and it consists of 4 subscales including tangible support, belonging support, self-esteem support, and appraisal support (Cohen & Hoberman, 1983)

On the real support subscale, individuals receive assistance from others in the form of actions or services, allowing them to overcome their procrastination problems. The individuals with self-esteem support receive encouragement that boosts their self-esteem, resulting in more positive feelings. Meanwhile, if this support is unavailable then the individual does not have self-meaningfulness and may view himself negatively. This leads to task delays because they feel unable to carry out work to completion. Also, individuals require assessment support in the form of suggestions or advice from friends or lecturers, hence avoiding procrastinating behavior. The availability of someone who can do something together prevents procrastination behavior that is reflected in belonging support.

Previous studies were carried out on social support and academic procrastination variables and the results showed a significant negative correlation. Lastary & Rahayu (2018) study entitled "The Relationship of Social Support and Self-Efficacy With Academic Procrastination of Overseas Students Studying in Jakarta". Sari & Fakhruddiana (2019) conducted a study titled "Internal Locus of Control, Social Support, and Academic Procrastination Among Students in Completing Thesis". The study by Amelia & Hadiwinarto (2020) entitled "The Relationship between Social Support and Academic Procrastination of Students in Class X Social Studies at SMA Negeri 2 Mukomuko". Further study by Amelia & Hadiwinarto (2020) entitled "Intrinsic Motivation, Social Support and Academic Procrastination of Students of the State Islamic Institute of Kerinci".

Based on the journal reviews, several works of literatures related the same variables of social support and academic procrastination as this study. However, the context of the respondents was different, namely final year students working on a thesis during the Covid-19 pandemic. The theory used is another difference, where the academic procrastination variable used Tuckman (1991) theory, while

the social support used the theory of Cohen & Hoberman (1983). Also, there were differences in topic authenticity and measuring instruments, including the Tuckman Procrastination Scale and the Interpersonal Support Evaluation List (ISEL). Previous studies discussed social support and academic procrastination in students working on a thesis, overseas, and senior high school students. Meanwhile, this study examines final year students working on a thesis during the pandemic.

II. METHODS

A non-experimental quantitative design was used, with a correlational method. The subjects include 161 final year students, male or female, currently working on a thesis during the Covid-19 pandemic. Also, the purposive sampling technique was used, which involves determining certain criteria (Sugiyono, 2008).

The 16-item short version of the Tuckman Procrastination Scale by Tuckman (1991) was used to measure the academic procrastination variable. This scale consists of three aspects, namely blaming others, delaying, and avoiding the task, with a Cronbach's alpha scale value of 0.82. The statement item is given a score on a 4-point Likert scale ranging from 1 to 4, indicating strongly disagree to very appropriate, respectively.

Furthermore, the 12-item Interpersonal Support Evaluation List by Cohen & Hoberman (1985) was used to measure social support, and Cronbach's alpha scale value was 0.80. The short version of the ISEL scale consists of 3 aspects, namely appraisal, tangible, and belonging support. Each statement item is scored on a 4-point Likert scale ranging from 1 to 4, indicating strongly disagree to very appropriate, respectively.

The data collection was carried out by distributing questionnaires to the subjects through a google form, based on the characteristics of the study. This process was conducted by sending broadcasts containing questionnaire links using social media such as WhatsApp, Line, Telegram, and Instagram. The one-time restriction setting was enabled for filling out google form links to minimize filling on the same subject.

The hypothesis proposed states that there is a significant negative relationship between social support and academic procrastination in students working on their thesis during the Covid-19 pandemic. Furthermore, the Statistical Product and Service Solutions (SPSS) version 24 for Windows was used to carry out the data analysis. Before the hypothesis was tested, several statistical tests were carried out, such as the assumption test which included the normality and linearity test. The Pearson Correlation parametric test was used for the hypothesis, while the additional analysis and different tests used the Pearson Correlation test and the Independent Sample T-Test, respectively.

III. RESULTS

The Q-Q Plots technique was used for the normality test. Furthermore, the data distribution is normal if the plot is

closer to the diagonal line, and it is not normally distributed if the plot is further away from the diagonal line.

Fig. 1: Academic Procrastination Variable Normality Test Results

Figure 1 demonstrated that the academic procrastination variable is normally distributed because the plots are closer to the diagonal (straight) line.

Fig. 2: Social Support Variable Normality Test Results

Based on the figure above, the social support variable data is normally distributed because the data distribution is closer to the diagonal line. The Compare Means technique was used to conduct the linearity test. Furthermore, the 2 variables have a linear relationship if the significance coefficient value is $p < 0.05$ and vice versa.

Variable	Linearity	F	P	Description
Academic Procrastination and Social Support	Linearity	26.663	0.000	Linear
	Deviation of Linearity	0.888	0.628	Not Deviating From Linear Line

Table 1: Linearity Test Results

Table 1 shows that the academic procrastination and social support variables have a linear relationship, and do not deviate from a straight line with an F value of 26,663 and a significance of $p = 0.000$ ($p < 0.05$). Meanwhile, the deviation value from linearity F and the value of p are 0.888 and 0.628, respectively. After the assumptions were tested, the Pearson Correlation parametric test technique was used to test the hypothesis because the data is normally distributed and linear.

Variable	Correlation Coefficient (r)	Significance (p)	Determinant Coefficient (r^2)	Description
Social Support and Academic Procrastination	-0.382	0.000	0.146	Significant

Table 2: Hypothesis Test Results

The correlation test results showed a significant negative correlation between social support and academic procrastination in final year students working on a thesis with r and p values of -0.382 and 0.000 ($p < 0.05$), respectively. Also, the coefficient of determination r^2 was 0.146, indicating an effective contribution of social support to academic procrastination of 14.6%.

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Procrastination	1	0.920**	0.844**	-0.380**	-0.310**	-0.260**	-0.405**
Academic Postponing tasks	0.920**	1	0.596**	-0.332**	-0.253**	-0.222**	-0.376**
Avoidance of tasks	0.844**	0.596**	1	-0.360**	-0.323**	-0.257**	-0.343**
Appraisal Support	-0.380**	-0.332**	-0.360**	1	0.841**	0.844**	0.788**
Tangible Support	-0.310**	-0.253**	-0.323**	0.841**	1	0.590**	0.447**
Belonging Support	-0.260**	-0.222**	-0.257**	0.844**	0.590**	1	0.524**
	-0.405**	-0.376**	-0.343**	0.788**	0.447**	0.524**	1

Table 3: Intercorrelation Test Results Aspects of Academic Procrastination with Social Support

** Correlation is significant $P < 0.05$

Table 3 showed that the strongest significant correlation is the belonging support and academic procrastination with $r = -0.405$ and $p < 0.05$, then the appraisal support with $r = -0.310$ and $p < 0.05$, while the tangible support aspect has $r = -0.260$ and $p < 0.05$.

Category	P	Mean
Male	0.895	38.17
Female		38.36

Table 4: Differences in Academic Procrastination Test Results Based on Gender

Table 4 depicted that there is no significant difference between academic procrastination in the male and female gender. However, the mean acquisition showed that female students have a higher level of academic procrastination than males.

Social Support and Academic Procrastination	(r)	(p)	Description
Male	-0.173	0.380	Not significant
Female	-0.435	0.000	Significant

Table 5: Additional Correlation Test Results Based on Gender

Table 5 shows an insignificant correlation between male subjects compared to female subjects. Therefore, the correlation between female and male subjects is fairly strong.

Category	P	Mean
Work/Part-time	0.943	38.39
Do not work		38.30

Table 6: Academic Procrastination Test Results Different Based on Employment Status

Table 6 demonstrated that there is no significant difference between who subjects work/part-time and those not working. However, the mean showed that working subjects have a higher level of procrastination.

Social Support and Academic Procrastination	(r)	(p)	Description
Work/Part-time	-0.452	0.001	Significant
Do not work	-0.357	0.000	Significant

Table 7: Additional Correlation Test Results Based on Employment Status

Table 7 showed a significant negative correlation between the variables of social support and academic procrastination in students who work and do not work, where working subjects have a fairly strong correlation compared to non-workers.

Category	P	Mean
Fast	0.627	38.12
Slow		38.66

Table 8: Academic Procrastination Difference Test Results Based on Lecturer Feedback

Table 8 depicted no significant difference between subjects who received fast and slow feedback, with a p-value of 0.627 ($p > 0.05$).

Social Support and Academic Procrastination	(r)	(p)	Description
Fast	-0.350	0.000	Significant
Slow	-0.431	0.000	Significant

Table 9: Additional Correlation Test Results Based on Lecturer Feedback

Table 9 indicated a significant negative correlation between the variables of social support and academic procrastination in subjects who received fast or slow feedback, where as subjects with slow feedback have a stronger correlation.

IV. DISCUSSION

The data processing results showed a significant negative relationship between the variables of social support and academic procrastination with the correlation coefficient value $r = -0.382$ and $p = 0.000$ ($p < 0.05$). Therefore, the hypothesis in this study is accepted. The coefficient of determination (r^2) was 0.146, indicating that the effective contribution of social support to academic procrastination is 14.6%. The other 85.4% are influenced by factors not examined in this study.

These results are in line with the study by (Lastary & Rahayu, 2018; Amelia & Hadiwinarto, 2020; Harmalis et al., 2021). This study also agrees with Sari & Fakhrudiana (2019) that social support has a significant negative correlation with student academic procrastination, indicated by a strong relationship strength, where $r = -0.618$ and $p < 0.05$. Hence, high social support leads to low individual procrastination, as the individuals become more motivated to complete their tasks.

Students working on their thesis require assessment, real, self-esteem, and a sense of belonging support to overcome the problem of academic procrastination. This type of support results in overall well-being because it exerts a positive influence, recognition of self-worth, a sense of predictability, and stability in an individual's life. Furthermore, integration into social networks helps an individual avoid the negative experiences (Cohen & Wills., 1985) caused by procrastination because they do not give up easily and can complete their thesis.

The intercorrelation test results showed a significant negative correlation that is strongest on the subscale of belonging support and academic procrastination, with $r = -0.405$ and $p < 0.05$. Furthermore, the appraisal support has a

significant correlation in the negative direction with an r-value of -0.310 and $p < 0.05$, while tangible support has an r-value of -0.260 and $p < 0.05$, indicating a significant negative relationship. These results demonstrate that social support can reduce student academic procrastination problems, especially when they receive belonging and appraisal support from the environment. Students with good belonging support complete their study period within the specified time, because they discuss and conduct other academic activities together with their friends (Anisahwati, 2019). The availability of someone who can carry out things together prevents prolonged procrastination. Moreover, students with appraisal support receive feedback, suggestions, or advice, hence it is easier to make revisions. The students with tangible support are optimistic about completing their thesis due to the assistance provided by others in the form of actions or services, hence procrastination is avoided.

According to the additional analysis test, there is no significant difference in the academic procrastination level of male or female subjects. These results are in line with a study by Astuti et al (2021) as well as Nilakantie and Mastuti (2014). The absence of differences is influenced by the demand to study independently (Astuti et al., 2021).

This study also showed a significant relationship between social support and academic procrastination in female students, whereas it was insignificant in the males. A previous study stated that women had a higher perceived level of social support than men. They have an affiliative style, with more attachments and wider social networks, than men due to the need for greater social support to maintain their psychological health (Soman et al., 2016). Therefore, the level of social support in men is low due to the lack of resources provided by one's interpersonal relationships, affecting the results.

The analysis of the procrastination test demonstrated that there is no significant difference between working/part-time and non-working subjects, and this was in line with study by Purwanto et al (2019). The reason for the absence of differences in work status is due to the ability to manage time well in both subjects, as well as being able to balance the need to study and work (Muzaqi & Arumsari, 2016).

The results of the correlation test based on employment status depicted that working subjects have a fairly strong correlation value compared to non-workers. However, the working subjects have more burdens and responsibilities due to differences in work and college activities. The students who study while working, are aware of the consequences, including the division of time, which may result in procrastination if mismanaged (Muzaqi & Arumsari, 2016). Therefore, these subjects require more social support from the environment to complete the thesis, hence reducing procrastination behavior.

The results of the different tests showed no difference in academic procrastination between students receiving fast and slow feedback. However, feedback from the lecturer, when working on a thesis, is important as procrastination behavior is minimized. Fritzsche et al (2003) reported that people who

procrastinate start working only when they receive feedback. This study found a significant relationship between feedback and delay in writing assignments. Also, feedbacks enable students to avoid technical errors in writing (Sholihat, 2021)

Furthermore, the results of the test show that students with slow feedback have a fairly strong correlation compared to those with fast feedback. This indicates that subjects with slow feedback require more social support while waiting for the lecturer's feedback. The support received makes the individual feel loved, cared for, and valued (Taylor et al., 2003).

This study is viable, though there are some limitations such as the difference in the number of respondents based on gender, where the female respondents dominate the male. Another limitation is that there is no semester limit for the subjects working on the thesis, and the criteria for those taking thesis courses are not added. Therefore, further studies are expected to include semester limits and the above criteria to facilitate the process of filtering the data used for the analysis.

V. CONCLUSIONS

Based on this study, there is a significant negative relationship between social support and academic procrastination in students working on a thesis during the Covid-19 pandemic. Therefore, the hypothesis proposed in this study is accepted.

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